

Engineering-geological modelling as a tool for modern archeological site preservation strategies

Feliziani F., Marmoni G.M., Gianni V., Grechi G., Felli G., Bozzano F., Martino S.

Sapienza University of Rome, Earth Sciences Department, P.le A. Moro 5, Rome, Italy

Traditionally, cultural heritage (CH) site conservation strategies have mostly focused on the employment of procedures to protect archaeological exhibits from weathering processes. However, CH-sites are often located in areas affected by geological hazards [1], which can threaten the conservation of the site itself. For these cases, engineering-geological modelling is an essential tool to design conservation strategies for geohazards management in the framework of CH-site preservation. The here proposed research is focused on the Punta Eolo promontory at Ventotene island (Italy) where the remnant of the roman "Villa Giulia" emperor palace is hosted. This latter is one of the pilot sites selected for the H2020 TRIQUETRA European project, aimed to proposing a methodological framework for mitigating climate-related natural hazards affecting cultural heritage.

Ventotene Island, together with the smaller Santo Stefano Island, represent the tip of a large stratovolcano built during the last 800,000 years [2]. The whole island is formed by a tuff plateau slightly dipping towards NE and bounded by active cliffs [3]. The Punta Eolo site is located in the northernmost sector of the island, where the volcanic deposit called Parata Grande Tuff (PGT) outcrops above lavas [2]. Due to their proximity to a rapidly retreating coastal cliff, the remains of Villa Giulia are vulnerable to landslides, which have already caused certain sections of the archeological site to collapse in the past.

Detailed engineering-geological surveying have been carried out at Punta Eolo. In particular, engineering-geological investigations have been coupled with remote investigation of the area of interest. Thanks to the engineering-geological surveys, detailed geological and geomorphological maps were drafted, also highlighting the geomechanical setting of the PGT. The presence of a superficial filling (SF), mainly composed of archaeological material overlaying the tuffaceous unit, was evidenced. To more effectively bound this layer's thickness, n. 60 single-station seismic noise measurements were carried out and were processed according to the Nakamura (1989) method [4]. Seismic ambient noise measurements show significant horizontal-to-vertical spectral ratio (HVSr) resonance peaks at 3 and 14 Hz, respectively related with the contact between the PGT and the underlying lavas and the SF and PGT units. The measurements conducted at the edge of the promontory show evidence of polarization of the particle motion potentially related to the vibrational behavior of the unstable rock blocks that bound all the site.

A 3D model of the cliff, reconstructed by drone photogrammetry technique, allowed to perform the rock mass joints surveying along the not-accessible cliff faces, as well as to visualize the SF thickness all around the perimeter of the promontory. Additionally, a 3D geological model was made using the RockWorks 16 program to facilitate a more direct visualization of site-specific features.

The here presented engineering-geological model enables the development of an efficient conservation strategy for the Villa Giulia archeological site, as a critical tool for mitigating the geological risks. Furthermore, future archaeological excavation will be driven by the reconstructed geological model of Punta Eolo.

References:

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